

CONTRASTIVE ANALYSIS OF THE NAMES OF NATIONAL GAMES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The development of world linguistics in the anthropocentric paradigm increases the need for research on the speech tools of the language, the effectiveness of the word, its place in the formation of the linguistic image of the world and its basic structure, rather than the natural existence in a comparative and comparative aspect.

Key words: Playfulness and creativity, linguistics, different linguistic and cultural traditions, comparative.

When talking about the interaction between language and culture, it is necessary to dwell in detail on the concept of "culture". There are many views on the interpretation of this concept. For example, G.V. Elizarova includes the concept of "culture" among axiomatic concepts that seem intuitively transparent. However, it is extremely difficult to define such a complex concept as culture. There are also definitions of culture that seek to capture the multifaceted nature of the concept, such as "Culture is how we live here." The initial approach to the definition of the concept of "culture" is based on the assumption that culture is a homogeneous state characteristic of all societies. Differences in society are interpreted not as differences in their essence and content, but as differences in the level of cultural development. As mankind progressed from savagery to civilization, culture served as a measure of progress in this process. The more signs of civilization were present in the life of a society, the more it was considered to be culturally advanced.

Descriptive adjectives: Many game names include descriptive adjectives that convey the nature or characteristics of the game. Examples include "Hot Potato" or "Red Light, Green Light." These linguistic features contribute to the playfulness and

engagement of children in the games and make the names more memorable and appealing. of the names. This analysis provides insights into the linguistic and cultural aspects of children's games and enhances our understanding of their significance and appeal. Some linguistic features commonly found in the names of children's games in Uzbek include: Similar to English, many game names in Uzbek use rhyming words or phrases to create a catchy and memorable name. For example, "Yosh bola" (Young Child) or "O'yin o'ynash" (Play and Have Fun). Uzbek game names also employ alliteration, where the same sound or letter is repeated at the beginning of multiple words in the name. Examples include "Bola bilan boshqotarish" (Playing with Children) or "Yomon yorug'lik" (Bad Behavior). Some game names in Uzbek use words that imitate the sounds associated with the game. For instance, "Chap-chap" (Clapping) or "Tik-tak" (Tick-Tock). Games may incorporate wordplay in Uzbek as well, adding humor or cleverness to the name. This could involve puns, double meanings, or playful combinations of words. An example is "Yolg'onchi qo'qon" (The Lying Hen), which plays on the idea of a deceitful hen. Many game names in Uzbek also include descriptive adjectives that convey the nature or characteristics of the game. Examples include "Qizil qo'ng'iroq" (Red Light) or "Yomon yorug'lik" (Bad Behavior).

Many game names in Uzbek also include descriptive adjectives that convey the nature or characteristics of the game. Examples include "Qizil qo'ng'iroq" (Red Light) or "Yomon yorug'lik" (Bad Behavior). These linguistic features contribute to the playfulness and engagement of children in the games and make the names more memorable and appealing in the Uzbek language.

In conclusion, the linguistic features commonly found in the names of children's games in Uzbek include rhyme, alliteration, onomatopoeia, wordplay, and descriptive adjectives. These features add playfulness, engagement, and memorability to the game names in the Uzbek language. The decay of any culture always happens in exactly one way - through the isolation of cultural elements, that is, when symbolism died as a result of changes in living conditions, language as a separate element of culture also died at the same time. Thus, language, thought, and culture are so closely

intertwined that in practice they form a threecomponent whole that none of these components can function (and therefore function) without the other two components. All of them together interact with the surrounding world, reflect it and shape it at the same time. In doing so, they create phenomena called worlds capes.

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